

GLOBAL GEOSIYOSIY KESKINLIK SHAROITIDA DAVLATLARNING IQTISODIY ERKINLIGINI TADQIQ ETISH: O‘ZBEKISTON MISOLIDA

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola global geosiyosiy tanglik sharoitida iqtisodiy erkinlikning zamonaviy tendensiyalarini o‘rganishga bag‘ishlangan. Unda iqtisodiy erkinlikning mohiyatiga indeksiy yondashuv va fazoviy tahlil asosida nazariy-metodologik asos keltirilgan. Maqolada mamlakatlarning yalpi ichki mahsuloti, ta‘lim tizimi va xalqaro savdo ko‘rsatkichlari bo‘yicha iqtisodiy erkinligi haqida tahliliy ma‘lumotlar taqdim etilgan. O‘zbekiston misolida iqtisodiy erkinlikning asosiy komponentlari – qonun ustuvorligi, davlat boshqaruvi shakli, tartibga soluvchi siyosatning samaradorligi va bozor ochiqqligi kabi jihatlar tahlil qilingan, mamlakat iqtisodiy taraqqiyotiga ta‘sir etuvchi muammoli jihatlar ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan. Xulosa qilinishicha, iqtisodiy erkinlik masalasi ko‘p qirrali, murakkab va ziddiyatli bo‘lib, u yanada chuqurroq tadqiqotlarni talab etadi hamda kelgusi ustuvor yo‘nalishlarni aniqlash imkonini beradi. Tahlil qilingan holatlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, iqtisodiy erkinlik zamonaviy globallashuv jarayonining ajralmas qismi bo‘lib, siyosiy va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni shakllantirishda muhim rol o‘ynaydi.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR

iqtisodiy erkinlik,
global iqtisodiyot,
geosiyosat, iqtisodiy
erkinlik indeksi,
modellari, strategiyalar,
fazoviy tahlil.

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СВОБОДЫ СТРАН В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ГЕОПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ НАПРЯЖЕННОСТИ: НА ПРИМЕРЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

Статья посвящена исследованию современных тенденций экономической свободы в условиях глобальной геополитической напряженности. В работе представлено теоретико-методологическое обоснование сущности современной парадигмы экономической свободы на основе индексного подхода и пространственного анализа. Предоставлена аналитическая информация об экономической свободе стран с учетом таких факторов, как ВВП, образование и международная торговля. Рассмотрены основные компоненты экономической свободы: верховенство закона, форма государственного управления, эффективность регуляторной политики и открытость рынка в Узбекистане, а также проанализированы проблемные аспекты, влияющие на экономическое развитие страны. Сделан вывод о том, что вопрос экономической свободы является многогранным, сложным и спорным феноменом, требующим дальнейшего изучения и позволяющим определить будущие приоритеты. В целом, проанализированные кейсы отражают общую тенденцию: экономическая свобода стран является неотъемлемой частью глобализованного мира и играет важную роль в формировании политических и социально-экономических процессов на фоне современных геополитических вызовов.

экономическая
свобода, глобальная
экономика, геополитика,
индекс экономической
свободы, модели,
стратегии,
пространственный
анализ.

RESEARCH ON THE ECONOMIC FREEDOM OF COUNTRIES IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL GEOPOLITICAL TENSION: THE CASE OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the research of current trends in economic freedom under conditions of global geopolitical tension. The paper provides a theoretical and methodological substantiation of the essence of the modern paradigm of economic freedom based on an index approach and spatial analysis. It presents analytical information on countries economic freedom in terms of GDP, education, and international trade. The main components of economic freedom are examined, namely, the rule of law, government format, effectiveness of regulatory policies and market openness in Uzbekistan, considering a range of problematic aspects influencing the country's economic development. It is concluded that the issue of economic freedom in countries is a multifaceted, complex and controversial phenomenon requiring further research and allowing for the identification of future priorities. Overall, the cases analyzed highlight the following common trend: the economic freedom of countries is an integral part of a globalized world and plays an important role in shaping political and socio-economic processes amid contemporary geopolitical challenges.

KEYWORDS

economic freedom, global economy, geopolitics, index of economic freedom, models, strategies, spatial analysis

Introduction

Maintaining and increasing the economic freedom of countries is an extremely relevant task amid the escalation of global geopolitical tensions observed in recent years. Overall, global challenges such as climate change, pandemics, and armed conflicts significantly impact the conditions for economic activity by economic agents across different regions of the world. These impacts manifest both directly, through economic and social changes, and indirectly, through the transformation of international economic relations and regulatory approaches. In such conditions, adaptation of national economies to new challenges becomes a necessary condition for ensuring their stability and competitiveness. Special attention is given to the concept of economic freedom, which allows for assessing how global transformations influence the functioning of market mechanisms and the efficiency of economic systems. It facilitates analysis of the economies' capacity to adapt, preserve free-market principles, and develop amidst constant changes.

Changes in the economic environment dictate the need to develop new strategies for managing the national economy and approaches that ensure sustainable development. Moreover, the process of post-crisis recovery of economies after global upheavals such as pandemics and military

conflicts requires an in-depth analysis of ways to overcome the consequences of crises and achieve economic stability. In this context, economic freedom indices play a significant role, enabling a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of economic policies and strategies, identifying strengths and weaknesses of a country's economic system, and forming strategies aimed at ensuring sustainable economic growth, adaptation to external and internal challenges, and maintaining stability amid crisis phenomena and other adverse factors.

The introduction of economic freedom indices and spatial analysis tools provides countries with instruments for assessing the state of the business environment and identifying avenues for its improvement. This creates preconditions for attracting significant investment resources, stimulating economic growth, and enhancing the efficiency of economic management. Thus, the study of the concept of economic freedom acquires particular importance in the context of modern global challenges and transformations.

Research results

The modern paradigm of economic freedom: theoretical discourse

Economic theory distinguishes two approaches to the study of economic freedom: narrow and broad ones. In the narrow sense, only economic freedom is studied, which is defined as the right of a person to freely dispose of their wealth,

income, time, and efforts. Proponents of the “narrow” approach give priority to economic freedom, recognizing its important role in the system of individual freedoms, as well as the connection between this freedom and other freedoms (political, intellectual ones). Economic freedom can function as a tool for achieving important personal goals or have independent value. The expansion of economic freedom with the expansion of choice applies not only to the consumption of goods and services, but also to other areas such as property, entrepreneurship, and investment.

Freedom, including economic freedom, in the process of rational choice is not limited to internal conditions of existence, but also involves the integration of rationality into the system of values of human life. Although reality often goes beyond rationality, it also has a certain mystical appeal. Rationality functions as a tool for overcoming limitations at a certain level, providing the opportunity to move to new, higher levels of freedom. When considering the freedom of a particular subject or group, it is defined as the ability to avoid restrictions, prohibitions, external interference, or obstacles that stand in the way of achieving a goal, completing a task, or becoming something, as well as the ability to determine what is impossible for others.

The practice of economic evolution confirms that the “modern market system, saturated with institutions,” is simultaneously effective, adaptive, innovative, and freer than other alternative systems, such as a command economy or traditional society. Understanding this paradox between order and freedom can be achieved through an analysis of the interaction between actors and institutions (Mamanazarov, et al., 2021).

Under conditions of economic transformation and decline, restrictions on economic freedoms have a much stronger impact than the expansion of social and political rights, since changes in the economic sphere directly affect people's material living conditions. One of the most common misconceptions is the perception of freedom as the unconditional acquisition of new rights and benefits without losing old opportunities and guarantees. This one-sided perception of freedom does not take into account the deep connection between concepts such as “freedom,” “independence,” and “responsibility.” Many people strive for freedom but are unwilling to take responsibility and act independently, hoping to preserve their privileges without any changes. This approach can lead to certain negative consequences, as freedom without responsibility can destabilize social and economic processes.

In the context of an innovation and investment model of economic growth, it is important to have a responsible entity that is capable of long-term rational planning and able to invest part of its income in capital development, innovation, and investment projects. In this process, the state acts not only as a source of necessity and regulation, but also as an institution that sets the “rules of the game” for free economic entities, protects property rights, and filters innovations. At the same time, the state sets limits at the level of social and economic norms, thus creating a framework for economic activity.

Thus, economic freedom encompasses the ability of economic actors to acquire property, choose how to use their knowledge and abilities, effectively manage resources, and distribute income within various forms of ownership and organizational and legal structures of economic activity. This freedom is the basis for the development of innovation, investment, and long-term economic growth, which contributes to the stable functioning of the economic system (Hamidov et al., 2020).

However, even with the growth of economic freedom, international relations face certain challenges, including inequality in the distribution of the benefits of economic growth, which can lead to social tensions and even cause confrontation among international partners. Conversely, in countries with low levels of economic freedom or ineffective institutions, inequality can deepen, creating risks for stability in regional and global geopolitical relations.

Analysis of economic freedom in countries around the world and in Europe in the context of geopolitical imbalances

Discussions and research on the role of economic freedom are largely focused on integrated indicators, including the Index of Economic Freedom (IEF) and the Index of Global Economic Freedom (IGEF).

The developers of these indices claim that they reflect changes in the principles of a free economy, such as objectively created market price distortions (leading to deviations from the optimal allocation of resources), significantly higher government taxes (which undermine incentives for investors and employees), and arbitrary restrictions on business activity (market entry, capital raising, investment, etc.).

The Economic Freedom Index is a comprehensive indicator of a country's economic freedom and consists of a number of sub-indices that take into account various aspects of economic activity and governance. Since different organizations use different assessment methods, the

weight of each indicator may vary in different publications.

The main components that are often taken into account in the Economic Freedom Index are as follows (Table 1).

Table 1

General approach to assessing economic freedom using the index method

Measurement	Criteria
Market openness	Degree and nature of tariffs and barriers to international trade. Freedom of capital and foreign investment.
Taxation level	The amount of taxes in relation to GDP. Different types of taxes and their rates
Level of regulation	The level of government intervention in the economy. Transparency and efficiency of administrative procedures
Currency stability	The level of inflation. Stability of the national currency.
Property protection	Protection of property rights. Efficiency of the judicial system.
Freedom to conduct business	Procedures for registering a business. Cost and time required for start-ups and business operations.
Freedom of work	Level of labor market regulation. Free access to labor and the labor market

Source: author's generalization

These indicators provide a comprehensive overview of a country's economic environment and determine its level of economic freedom. The Economic Freedom Index is used to compare the level of economic freedom in different countries and identify trends in economic development. It is calculated based on a number of indicators that assess a country's level of economic freedom.

The Economic Freedom Index is based on 10 indicators and is rated on a scale from 0 to 100, with 100 representing maximum freedom. Each of the 10

factors is considered to be of equal importance, so this overall index represents the arithmetic mean of the indicators. All countries are divided into the following groups according to this index: free — score of 80–100 (3% of countries worldwide); mostly free — score of 70–79.9 (17% of countries worldwide); moderately free — score of 60–69.9 (35% of countries worldwide); largely unfree — score of 50–59.9 (35% of countries worldwide); despotic — score of 0–49.9 (10% of countries worldwide) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Top 20 countries by level of economic freedom, 2024.

Source: compiled by the authors in the dashboard knoema.com

Countries with the highest economic freedom indices are usually characterized as “fully free” in their economic development, which means minimal restrictions on business, low market regulation, and free access to resources and labor markets. A high level of economic freedom provides favorable conditions for the development of entrepreneurship, investment, and innovation, leading to higher economic growth and prosperity for citizens. In particular, such countries have effective institutions for protecting property rights, stable financial systems, and low levels of corruption.

On the other hand, countries with low economic freedom indices tend to be characterized by significant market restrictions, high barriers to entry into business, excessive bureaucracy, and restrictions on entrepreneurial freedom. These factors stifle economic activity, which usually leads to low levels of economic development, high unemployment, and poverty. Such countries often include the least developed economies, particularly in Southeast Asia and Africa, as well as some oil-producing countries such as Libya, Venezuela, and Iran, where economic freedom is limited due to state intervention and control over resources.

It is important to note that economic indices are not a direct indicator of the overall level of economic freedom, as they reflect the degree to which an economic system approximates the ideal of a liberal economy. The ideal of a liberal economy includes not only the absence of market restrictions and a minimal role for the state, but also favorable macroeconomic conditions, which imply low inflation, moderate taxes, a balanced state budget, and the absence of large public debts. In this context, the role of the state is limited to providing basic functions such as protecting property rights, maintaining law and order, ensuring personal safety, and enforcing contracts.

The pursuit of greater economic freedom not only opens up new opportunities for economic agents—consumers and producers—but also plays a critical role in creating economically stable and prosperous societies, allowing people to have more choices, promoting innovation, increasing resource efficiency, and creating competitive markets, which in turn leads to an improvement in the overall economic situation.

Thus, in 2024, the difference between countries in the world in terms of the Economic Freedom Index is very large, indicating global polarization. The gap between the tigers in North America, Northern Europe, Australia, and Asia and the rest of the world reaches 22-25%, and even in

Europe, the situation varies in terms of economic freedom (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Clustering of European countries by economic freedom index

Source: Heritage Foundation built-in tool, 2024.

There is a significant range of economic freedom in EU countries. Countries such as the Netherlands, Denmark, and Switzerland may have a high economic freedom index, measured by market flexibility, effective justice, and investment climate,

However, other countries may face problems such as excessive government regulation and high taxes (Botelho, et al., 2024). The dynamics of the Economic Freedom Index in some EU countries in 2024 are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. – Index of Economic Freedom in selected European countries in 2024.

Source: constructed by the authors in the dashboard knoema.com

Despite varying levels of economic freedom, EU countries show certain differences in growth dynamics depending on whether they are members of the Eurozone or not (Figure 4).

Figure 4. – Index of economic freedom in Eurozone and other countries, 2024.

Source: created by the authors in the dashboard knoema.com

Eurozone countries showed a more cautious growth rate and a more significant decline in the economic freedom ranking compared to countries that do not use the euro. For example, although Slovakia rose 7 positions, its neighbor Slovenia, which is almost the same size, lost 14 positions. On the other hand, among non-eurozone countries, Poland improved its position, rising 8 places, while the decline in countries such as Hungary and Sweden was minimal (3 places down). Overall indicators confirm this trend: among Eurozone countries, the average decline is one position, while the average for non-Eurozone countries shows an increase of two positions. These data suggest that the absence of the euro as a currency may be associated with more successful progress in the global economic freedom ranking over the past year.

A study of the dynamics of the economic freedom index in the Eastern Partnership countries showed quite interesting results (Figure 5).

Figure 5. – Dynamics of the economic freedom index in the Eastern Partnership countries, 2023.

Source: constructed by the authors in the dashboard knoema.com

The Economic Freedom Index in the Eastern Partnership countries (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine) reflects the level of economic freedom in these countries. The index value can have a significant impact on economic development, investment, and overall well-being in the region.

In the Eastern Partnership countries, the level of economic freedom is determined by a number of factors:

- investment attractiveness: countries with a high level of economic freedom are usually considered attractive to foreign investors. Reduced restrictions on entrepreneurial activity, transparency of governance, and low levels of corruption can stimulate investment and business development;

- market efficiency: a high score means that markets are flexible and economic processes are efficient, which promotes entrepreneurship and competition;

- job creation: improving the business environment and increasing economic activity will lead to the creation of new jobs and higher employment rates;

- standard of living: higher indices indicate a higher standard of living thanks to economic growth, expanded business opportunities, and reduced poverty;

- international competitiveness, namely, reducing bureaucratic barriers and improving the business environment can increase the international competitiveness of Eastern Partnership countries in the global market.

A study of economic freedom in the G7 countries provided the following results (Figure 6).

Figure 6. – Economic freedom in the G7 countries, 2023.

Source: constructed by the authors in the dashboard knoema.com

The analysis data show that the economic freedom of world economic leaders demonstrates significant divergence. In the period before the pandemic crisis, Canada, the United Kingdom, and the United States were the leaders in terms of economic freedom, but by 2023, this indicator had significantly decreased, giving way to Germany.

Therefore, when examining the key triggers for the development of economic freedom in the context of contemporary global challenges, it is important to bear in mind the following points.

First, countries with greater economic freedom have stronger economies and higher GDP per capita (Figure 7).

Figure 7. – Economic freedoms relative to GDP, 2024.

Source: Heritage Foundation built-in toolkit

Second, on average, citizens of economically free countries receive twice as much formal education as citizens of economically depressed countries (Figure 8).

Figure 8. – Economic freedoms relative to educational attainment, 2024.

Source: Heritage Foundation built-in tool

Third, free trade is an important element of economic freedom. Countries that embrace free trade ultimately achieve greater prosperity (Figure 9).

Figure 9. – Economic freedoms relative to trade, 2024.

Source: Heritage Foundation built-in tool

Although there is no single “golden formula” for ensuring sustainable economic development, scientific research and economic freedom rankings provide important clues and indicators for understanding how countries can achieve prosperity. One key finding is that governments that encourage open economies and support free markets create favorable conditions for innovation, business, and entrepreneurship, which ultimately leads to economic development and higher living standards for their citizens.

In particular, countries that actively promote economic liberalization, reduce government intervention, lower barriers to entrepreneurship and investment, and encourage the free movement of goods, services, and capital rank higher in economic freedom rankings. These countries tend to have high levels of innovation, well-functioning labor and capital markets, and high levels of economic stability, which allows them to adapt more quickly to change, generate economic growth, and ensure a high level of well-being for their citizens.

In contrast, countries with low economic freedom indices typically face economic difficulties such as low investment, high barriers to entrepreneurship, and significant government intervention, which often leads to less efficient use of resources, labor market instability, and limited opportunities for innovation.

Theoretical and practical conclusions from the analysis of economic freedom indices indicate that there is a clear correlation between the level of economic freedom and economic growth. Countries that adhere to the principles of a liberal economy tend to have higher GDP growth rates, higher levels of investment, and better indicators in terms of employment and citizen income (Mamanazarov, et al., 2024).

Research on current trends in economic freedom in Uzbekistan

According to data from the American analytical center The Heritage Foundation, the Republic of Uzbekistan is defined as an “almost unfree” country in the world. According to this rating, Uzbekistan's economic freedom index in 2024 was 56.0 out of 100 points, placing the country 109th out of 184 countries worldwide (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Dynamics of the Economic Freedom Index in Uzbekistan

Source: Heritage Foundation tools

The country's economic freedom index has fallen by 1.0 points since the last study, but has maintained and improved its position by 8 points: freedom of business, trade, currency, investment, finance, property rights, corruption, and labor, according to the Heritage Foundation in its annual Index of Economic Freedom.

According to experts, Uzbekistan continues to implement policies to accelerate economic freedom, transition to greater openness, and modernization. For comparison, among the countries of Central Asia, Kazakhstan ranks 71st and is considered a relatively free economy (although it ranked 34th in the 2021 ranking), Kyrgyzstan ranks

115th and Tajikistan ranks 146th, which are almost non-free economies, and Turkmenistan ranks 161st and is a repressive economy.

Low Economic Freedom Index scores were clear indicators of institutional shortcomings in key areas such as transparency, efficiency, and openness, which prevented Uzbekistan from fully realizing its economic potential. Of the 10 economic freedoms studied, the country improved its scores in five, including property rights, judicial efficiency, government integrity, monetary freedom, and tax policy; four remained unchanged: investment, labor freedom, trade freedom, and financial freedom; and one deteriorated in government spending (Table 2).

Table 2

Criteria of Uzbekistan economic freedoms assessment

Components	Year							
	2024	2023	2022	2021	2020	2019	2018	2017
Overall	56,0	57,0	56,0	58,0	57,0	53,0	52,0	52,0
Business freedom	61,0	59,0	59,0	74,0	73,0	73,0	67,0	65,0
Trade freedom	76,0	76,0	76,0	55,0	68,0	63,0	63,0	67,0
Government spending	72,0	85,0	97,0	92,0	92,0	91,0	91,0	91,0
Monetary freedom	63,6	63,4	61,6	60,3	59,9	58,9	61,9	61,1
Investment freedom	60,0	60,0	50,0	20,0	20,0	10,0	0,00	0,00
Financial freedom	50,0	50,0	40,0	20,0	20,0	10,0	10,0	10,0

Property rights protection	33,0	31,0	32,0	58,0	59,0	50,0	49,0	48,0
Freedom from corruption	29,0	25,0	24,0	31,0	28,0	25,0	24,0	28,0
Labor freedom	48,0	48,0	48,0	61,0	60,0	59,0	52,0	50,0

Source: compiled by the authors based on: Heritage Foundation, 2024

Uzbekistan, while remaining a country with a low level of economic freedom among Central Asian and world countries, demonstrates that even previously adopted correct decisions had a significant effect but were implemented slowly, which made it impossible to achieve the expected results. For comparison, the average global economic freedom index in 2024 for 184 countries was 59.0 points, and only four countries and regions are economically free: Singapore, Switzerland, Ireland, and Taiwan.

The authors' analysis of the dynamics of Uzbekistan's economic freedom index allowed them to agree on the effective functioning of key components, namely the rule of law, regulatory policy, government activity, and market openness (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Economic Freedom Index: rule of law, regulatory policy, government activity, and market openness

Source: author's summary

The study highlights a number of problematic aspects that affect the development of Uzbekistan, but researchers emphasize the extreme importance of expanding economic freedoms and increasing economic growth, which underscores the importance of studying economic freedom in the country. In addition, according to the authors, it is necessary to clearly define the basic principles of the state's economic policy, which will increase the level of economic freedom by improving institutional components, property rights, reducing inflationary pressure, and increasing the investment attractiveness of the national currency.

However, before developing specific reforms to improve the economic situation, it is important to carefully explore the optimal ways to implement them, in particular, to determine whether the reforms should be gradual or radical, and whether they should cover individual sectors of the economy or several sectors at once. Resolving these

issues will significantly affect the effectiveness of reforms and the achievement of the strategic goal of improving the economic situation in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Conclusions

In the context of escalating global geopolitical challenges, the issue of economic freedom is becoming particularly important for both national economies and the international system of economic relations. An analysis of the dynamics of economic freedom in different countries shows that its growth is a key factor for economic prosperity and stability, while a decline in economic freedom is accompanied by a slowdown in development, a loss of investment attractiveness, and economic instability.

Global tensions in recent years have led to a radical review of economic development strategies and the need to adapt to new realities. Developed countries, which traditionally rely on international trade as a source of growth, are forced to rethink

their trade policies, strengthening measures to diversify supplies, strengthen domestic markets, and create new logistics routes that reduce dependence on unstable partners.

Economic freedom is not only an economic indicator but also an element of national security that requires systemic reforms to ensure the stable functioning of market mechanisms and the need for accelerated economic transformation based on the principles of the rule of law, free competition, the fight against corruption, the protection of property rights, and effective public administration.

In this context, increasing economic freedom should become a strategic priority for countries, and Uzbekistan in particular, that are striving for sustainable development, as it provides the necessary flexibility of the economic system, its adaptability to new challenges, and its ability to recover quickly. In general, in today's environment, economic freedom is not only an indicator of economic development, but also a factor that determines the stability of states in crisis situations, and therefore ensuring it should be one of the key priorities of economic policy on a global geopolitical scale.

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